

F₂ distribution of TMR, TSV, and SLW in the cross of Guichao 2/82-856F₂.

72.52% for SLW, 66.19% for TMR, and 33.84% for TSV.

This suggests that SLW and TSV had multigenic and additive actions and that

TMR was controlled by some major genes and a small number of dominant genes with cumulative and unequal effect. ■

Photoperiod sensitivity of traditional rice variety of Andamans

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Local rice variety C14-8 occupies more than 50% of the rice area in Andamans. We compared its photoperiod sensitivity

with the moderate photoperiod sensitivity of modern variety CR1009 at 12° N lat. and 92-94° E long. The crops were sown on the 10th d of each month for 1 yr.

CR1009 sown in Oct flowered in 100 d. When sown in Mar and Apr, it flowered in 130 d (Fig. 1). C14-8 sown in Nov flowered in 115 d. When sown in Dec, it flowered in 341 d, the difference being 226 d. The basic vegetative phase

1. Days to flowering of rice varieties sown in different months.

2. Variation in daylength and temperature during different months in Port Blair, India.

of CR1009 was about 65 d and that of C14-8 80 d. The photoperiod-sensitive phase was about 30 and 226 d, respectively.

The marked difference in flowering durations with month of sowing is attributed mainly to response to varying daylengths in different months (Fig. 2). Variation in days to flowering was caused by difference in vegetative lag phase only. The basic vegetative, reproductive, and ripening phases were constant in both varieties.

C14-8 is highly sensitive to slight variations in daylength, indicating strong photoperiod sensitivity. ■

Association of rice ratooning ability and vigor with grain yield

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We evaluated rice ratooning ability, vigor, and yield in 22 rice cultivars during 1987 wet season. The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. At harvest, the main crop was cut leaving a 15 cm culm. The stubble was irrigated 3 d after harvest and 40 kg N/ha applied 7 d after harvest.

Ratoon vigor was assessed as 1 = extra vigorous, 5 = intermediate or normal, 9 = very weak. A ratoon rating (RR) was calculated as

$$RR = (1 - [0.1 \text{ ratoon vigor}]^{\text{av number of ratoon tillers/plant}})$$

Ratoon grain yield (t/ha)

Relationship between ratoon rating and ratoon grain yield in 22 rice cultivars. ACRI, Tamil Nadu, India, 1987 wet season.

The association between RR and ratoon yield was positive and significant (see figure). Most cultivars with high RR had high ratoon yield. RR can be used as a criterion in selecting rice cultivars for high ratooning ability. ■

Effect of leaf senescence and stubble carbohydrate content on ratoon rice yield

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We studied the relationship between carbohydrate content in the stubble and leaf senescence at main harvest and ratoon yield in rice genotypes Bhavani, MDU3, IET6262, IET6709, IET7552, and IET9235 and their crosses during Oct 1988.

Each entry was planted in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 10-cm spacing, in a randomized block design with three replications. Recommended practices were followed for both main and ratoon crops. Ten randomly selected plants of each parent and cross from each replication were used to estimate main crop stubble carbohydrate content, leaf senescence, and ratoon yield.

Total carbohydrate content was estimated by phenol sulfuric acid method. Leaf senescence was estimated by

$$\% \text{ senescent} = \frac{\text{Total number senescent leaves}}{\text{Total number green leaves at milk stage}} \times 100$$

Relationship of carbohydrate content in stubble and leaf senescence at harvest to ratoon yield^a Madurai, India 1988.

Parent, cross	Carbohydrate content of stubble (%)	Leaf senescence (%)	Ratoon yield (g/10 plants)
Bhavani	20.5	55.2	14.4
MDU3	17.8	51.4	12.3
IET6262	21.2	57.6	12.8
IET6709	23.2	52.9	13.6
IET7552	18.8	60.8	15.1
IET9239	24.2	59.6	11.7
Bhavani/MDU3	18.6 (18.2)	54.0 (53.4)	14.5 (12.5)
Bhavani/IET6262	21.2 (19.4)	54.9 (54.2)	16.1 (13.2)
Bhavani/IET6729	20.7 (19.7)	51.2 (58.0)	15.4 (15.1)
Bhavani/IET7552	19.7 (20.9)	66.3 (58.7)	14.9 (16.3)
Bhavani/IET9239	20.6 (22.0)	55.0 (58.2)	14.3 (12.8)
MDU3/IET6262	17.6 (16.7)	52.0 (56.3)	12.8 (13.5)
MDU3/IET6709	20.2 (21.5)	51.4 (50.4)	13.1 (13.7)
MDU3/IET7552	17.8 (16.7)	51.7 (56.0)	12.4 (15.0)
MDU3/IET9239	19.4 (21.2)	56.8 (66.3)	12.5 (11.9)
IET6262/IET6709	22.0 (23.8)	58.4 (56.2)	14.4 (15.2)
IET6262/IET7552	17.5 (19.0)	62.2 (60.1)	13.0 (15.1)
IET6262/IET9239	21.7 (25.2)	52.9 (58.5)	12.8 (12.5)
IET6709/IET7552	20.7 (22.3)	56.5 (55.2)	15.2 (16.8)
IET6709/IET9239	24.8 (23.8)	52.5 (54.9)	13.5 (12.6)
IET7552/IET9239	22.6 (20.2)	62.5 (56.5)	15.9 (12.0)
Mean: Parent	20.95	56.26	13.32
cross	20.52	55.71	13.96
SE	0.43	0.94	0.28
LSD (P = 0.05)	1.22	2.65	0.78
Correlation with ratoon yield	0.0137 ^{ns}	0.2136 ^{ns}	

^aFigures in parentheses are for reciprocal cross.

IET7552 and Bhavani had the highest ratoon yields (see table). The effects of carbohydrate content of the stubble and leaf senescence at harvest on ratoon yield

were not significant, indicating low influence of these factors on ratoon yield. This emphasizes the importance of inherent ratooning ability of parents. ■

Effect of high humidity and low temperature on spikelet fertility in indica rice

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Rains, high humidity, and low temperature lower spikelet fertility in first crop indica rice and could increase percentage of empty spikelets and reduce yields. We studied the effect of such wet weather on 12 indica varieties in 1989.

Spikelet fertility percentage (SFP) was measured on 6-10 randomly selected panicles at heading. SFP was reduced with increased humidity and decreased temperature (see figure). The most important meteorological factor was relative humidity ($r = -0.96^*$), followed by mean temperature 3 d after heading.

Response of 3 groups of indica varieties to relative humidity and daily mean temperature at heading and flowering. Hangzhou, China, 1989.